

CYLINDRICAL BENDING OF LAMINATED ANISOTROPIC PLATES INCLUDING TRANSVERSE SHEAR DEFORMATION

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ABSTRACT

A closed form solution is obtained for cylindrical bending of a laminated, anisotropic plate subjected to a uniform transverse load. The governing equations include the effect of transverse shear deformation. Numerical examples are presented for clamped and simply-supported boundary conditions in conjunction with a $[\pm 45^\circ]_S$ laminate. These results show that the effect of transverse shear deformation depends on both the boundary conditions and bending-twisting coupling.

INTRODUCTION

Numerous solutions have been published for laminated plates based on classical Kirchhoff assumptions. It is well recognized, however, that shear deformation can be more significant in laminated, anisotropic plates than in isotropic, homogeneous plates. This is due to the large ratios of effective inplane tensile moduli to through-the-thickness shear moduli.

Shear deformation theories based on Mindlin's assumptions have been developed for laminated, anisotropic plates^{1,2}. Although analytical solutions to these theories have been obtained for specially orthotropic laminates, few solutions can be found for laminated, anisotropic plates (non-zero bending-twisting coupling). In this paper closed form solutions are obtained for the cylindrical bending of symmetrically laminated anisotropic plates subjected to a uniform lateral pressure.

GOVERNING EQUATIONS

Let us consider a symmetric laminate of thickness h with the axes system in the mid-plane. The inplane coordinates are denoted by x , y , and the thickness coordinate by z . If the length in the y -direction is much longer than the x -direction, and the laminate is subjected to a lateral load which is independent of y , then the resulting deformations will be independent of y . Such cases are referred to as cylindrical bending. For the case of cylindrical bending, the displacements in conjunction with a shear deformation type of plate theory are of the form

$$u = z \psi_x(x), \quad v = z \psi_y(x), \quad w = w(x) \quad (1)$$

where ψ_x and ψ_y are the rotations relative to the x and y axes, respectively. Under these assumptions the governing equations are of the form

$$D_{11} \frac{d^2 \psi_x}{dx^2} + D_{16} \frac{d^2 \psi_y}{dx^2} - k_3 A_{45} \psi_y - k_2 A_{55} \left(\psi_x + \frac{dw}{dx} \right) = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$D_{16} \frac{d^2 \psi_x}{dx^2} + D_{66} \frac{d^2 \psi_y}{dx^2} - k_1 A_{44} \psi_y - k_3 A_{45} \left(\psi_x + \frac{dw}{dx} \right) = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$k_2 A_{55} \left(\frac{d\psi_x}{dx} + \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} \right) + k_3 A_{45} \frac{d\psi_y}{dx} + q = 0 \quad (4)$$

where k_i are shear correction factors and

$$A_{ij} = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} C_{ij} dz \quad i, j = 4, 5$$

$$D_{ij} = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} Q_{ij} z^2 dz \quad i, j = 1, 6$$

In addition, C_{ij} and Q_{ij} are the shear stiffnesses and reduced stiffnesses for plane stress, respectively. The lateral load is represented by

$$q = \sigma_z(x, h/2) - \sigma_z(x, -h/2)$$

where σ_z is the normal stress through-the-thickness of the plate.

In the present paper closed form solutions will be obtained to eqs (2-4) for the uniform load $q = q_0 = \text{constant}$. Two boundary conditions will be considered: clamped supports and simple-supports. Numerical results will be presented which allow one to investigate the effects of shear deformation, laminate stacking sequence, boundary conditions, plate length-to-thickness ratio, and bending-twisting coupling of symmetrically laminated plates subjected to cylindrical bending.

It should be noted that the cylindrical bending of laminated plates analyzed by the classical Kirchhoff theory³ does not result in governing equations which include the bending-twisting coupling term, D_{16} . Thus, the present theory allows one to investigate the effect of bending-twisting coupling. In addition, the solution presented in this paper represents new results for laminated plate analysis with shear deformation included.

SOLUTION FOR UNIFORM TRANSVERSE LOADING

Let us now consider the case where the plate is loaded with a uniform transverse load $q = q_0 = \text{constant}$. A solution to eqs. (2-4) is of the form

$$\psi_x = c_1 + c_2 x + c_3 \frac{x^2}{2} - \frac{D_{16}}{D_{11}} (A \cosh \lambda \frac{x}{h} + B \sinh \lambda \frac{x}{h}) - \frac{q_0 x^3}{6D_{11}} \quad (5)$$

$$\psi_y = F_1 (c_3 - \frac{q_0}{D_{11}} x) + A' \cosh \lambda \frac{x}{h} + B \sinh \lambda \frac{x}{h} \quad (6)$$

$$w = c_4 - c_1 x - c_2 \frac{x^2}{2} + (6F_3 - x^2) \frac{x}{6} c_3 - (12F_2 - x^2) \frac{x^2}{24D_{11}} q_0 + \frac{hF_3}{\lambda} (A \sinh \lambda \frac{x}{h} + B \cosh \lambda \frac{x}{h}) \quad (7)$$

where

$$\lambda = \left[\frac{(k_1 k_2 A_{44} A_{55} - k_3^2 A_{45}^2) D_{11} h^2}{(k_2 A_{55} (D_{11} D_{66} - D_{16}^2))} \right]^{1/2}, \quad F_1 = \frac{(k_2 A_{55} D_{16} - k_3 A_{45} D_{11})}{(k_1 k_2 A_{44} A_{55} - k_3^2 A_{45}^2)},$$

$$F_2 = \frac{(k_1 A_{44} D_{11} - k_3 A_{45} D_{16})}{(k_1 k_2 A_{44} A_{55} - k_3^2 A_{45}^2)}, \quad F_3 = \frac{(k_2 A_{55} D_{16} - k_3 A_{45} D_{11})}{k_2 A_{55} D_{11}}$$

We now consider two sets of boundary conditions: clamped and simply-supported. The width of the plate is denoted by a and the axis system is placed at the middle such that the boundaries are located at $x = \pm a/2$. In this case w will be symmetric about $x = 0$, while both ψ_x and ψ_y are anti-symmetric. This leads to the result

$$c_1 = c_3 = A = 0 \quad (8)$$

1. Clamped Boundaries

$$\text{at } x = \pm a/2, w = \psi_x = \psi_y = 0 \quad (9)$$

This leads to the result

$$c_2 = \frac{(24F_1D_{16} + D_{11}a^2)}{24D_{11}^2} q_0, \quad B = \frac{F_1a}{2D_{11}\sinh \lambda \frac{a}{2h}} q_0, \quad (10)$$

$$c_4 = \left\{ [48(F_2D_{11} + F_1D_{16}) + D_{11}a^2] \lambda a - 192hF_1F_3D_{11}\tanh \lambda \frac{a}{2h} \right\} \frac{a}{384\lambda D_{11}^2} q_0$$

The maximum deflection will occur at the center of the plate, $x = 0$, and is given by the relationship

$$w_{\max} = \frac{w_{\text{CLPT}}}{\lambda a^3 D_{11}} \left\{ [48(F_2D_{11} + F_1D_{16}) + D_{11}a^2] \lambda a + 192hF_1F_3D_{11} \frac{(\cosh \lambda \frac{a}{2h} - 1)}{\sinh \lambda \frac{a}{2h}} \right\} \quad (11)$$

where w_{CLPT} is the maximum deflection as determined from classical laminated plate theory with shear deformation neglected and is of the form

$$\frac{a^4}{384D_{11}} q_0 \quad (12)$$

We note that the classical solution is independent of the bending-twisting coupling stiffness D_{16} . For the case of an orthotropic material $A_{45} = D_{16} = 0$ and eq. (11) reduces to

$$w_{\max} = w_{\text{CLPT}} \left(1 + \frac{48D_{11}}{k_2 A_{55} a^2} \right) \quad (13)$$

2. Simply-Supported Boundaries

$$\text{at } x = \pm a/2, w = M_x = M_{xy} = 0 \quad (14)$$

where

$$M_x = D_{11} \frac{\partial \psi_x}{\partial x} + D_{16} \frac{\partial \psi_y}{\partial x}, \quad M_{xy} = D_{16} \frac{\partial \psi_x}{\partial x} + D_{66} \frac{\partial \psi_y}{\partial x}$$

Thus, vanishing of the bending moment M_x and the twisting moment M_{xy} requires that

$$\text{at } x = \pm a/2, \frac{\partial \psi_x}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial \psi_y}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (15)$$

Equations (14) and (15) lead to the results

$$c_2 = \frac{(8F_1D_{16} + D_{11}a^2)}{8D_{11}^2} q_0, \quad B = \frac{F_1h}{\lambda D_{11} \cosh \lambda \frac{a}{2h}} q_0, \quad (16)$$

$$c_4 = \frac{\{ [48(F_2D_{11} + F_1D_{16}) + 5D_{11}a^2] \lambda^2 a^2 - 384h^2 F_1 F_3 D_{11} \} q_0}{384 \lambda^2 D_{11}^2}$$

Again the maximum deflection occurs at the center of the plate with the result

$$w_{\max} = \frac{w_{\text{CLPT}}}{5\lambda^2 a^4 D_{11}} \{ [48(F_2D_{11} + F_1D_{16}) + 5D_{11}a^2] \lambda^2 a^2 + 384h^2 F_1 F_3 D_{11} \frac{(\cosh \lambda \frac{a}{2h} - 1)}{\cosh \lambda \frac{a}{2h}} \} \quad (17)$$

where

$$\frac{5a^4}{384D_{11}} q_0$$

For the case of an orthotropic material $A_{45} = D_{16} = 0$ and eq. (17) reduces to

$$w_{\max} = w_{\text{CLPT}} \left(1 + \frac{48D_{11}}{5k_2 A_{55} a^2} \right) \quad (18)$$

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We now consider a $[\pm 45^\circ]_S$ laminate with the following normalized stiffness properties:

$$D_{16}/D_{11} = 0.5503, \quad D_{12}/D_{11} = 0.7608, \quad D_{66}/D_{11} = 0.8127, \quad (19)$$

$$k_1 A_{44} h^2 / D_{11} = k_2 A_{55} h^2 / D_{11} = 1.009, \quad A_{45} = 0$$

The shear correction factors are chosen as the classical values $k_1 = k_2 = 5/6$. The properties given in eq. (18) are typical of state-of-the-art fiber reinforced composite materials.

For this case the expressions for maximum deflection, eqs. (11) and (17), reduce to the following

$$w_{\max} = w_{\text{CLPT}} \left[1 + 48 \frac{(D_{11}^2 + D_{16}^2)}{k_1 A_{44} h^2 D_{11} \bar{a}^2} + 192 \frac{D_{16}^2}{k_1 A_{44} h^2 D_{11} \lambda \bar{a}^3} \frac{(\cosh \lambda \bar{a}/2 - 1)}{\sinh \lambda \bar{a}/2} \right] \quad (20)$$

for clamped boundaries and

$$w_{\max} = w_{\text{CLPT}} \left[1 + 48 \frac{(D_{11}^2 + D_{16}^2)}{5k_1 A_{44} h^2 D_{11} \bar{a}^2} + 384 \frac{D_{16}^2}{5k_1 A_{44} h^2 D_{11} \lambda^2 \bar{a}^4} \frac{(\cosh \lambda \bar{a}/2 - 1)}{\cosh \lambda \bar{a}/2} \right] \quad (21)$$

for simply-supported boundaries. In these relationships $\bar{a} = a/h$. Numerical results from eqs. (20) and (21) are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Normalized maximum deflections, w_{\max}/w_{CLPT}

a/h	CC		SS	
	Eq. (20)	Eq. (13)	Eq. (21)	Eq. (18)
5	3.787	2.903	1.527	1.381
10	1.661	1.476	1.126	1.095
15	1.288	1.211	1.055	1.042
20	1.160	1.119	1.031	1.024
25	1.102	1.076	1.020	1.015
30	1.070	1.053	1.014	1.011
35	1.052	1.039	1.010	1.008
40	1.039	1.030	1.007	1.006

In Table 1, CC and SS denote clamped and simply-supported boundaries, respectively.

It is clear from the results presented in Table 1 that the effect of shear deformation depends on the boundary conditions. In particular, the effect of shear deformation in conjunction with clamped boundaries is much more severe than in the case of simply-supported boundaries. We also note that the bending twisting shear coupling term, D_{16} , has an effect on shear deformation, i.e., larger values of a/h are required in order to dissipate the effects of shear deformation compared to the orthotropic plate in which $D_{16} = 0$. The orthotropic case represents the solution for a symmetric angle-ply laminate with many layers. In particular, for the class of laminates $[\pm 45^\circ]_{NS}$, $D_{16} \rightarrow 0$ as $N \rightarrow \infty$. In this context, N denotes the number of $\pm 45^\circ$ units above the midplane.

In conclusion, closed form solutions have been developed for the bending of a laminated, anisotropic plate subjected to a uniform transverse load. The governing equations include the effect of transverse shear deformation. Although the solution is applicable to any combination of classical boundary conditions, clamped and simply-supported edges were considered in the numerical examples. Results for a $[\pm 45^\circ]_S$ show that the effects of shear deformation depend on the boundary conditions and are more severe for anisotropic plates ($D_{16} \neq 0$) than for orthotropic plates ($D_{16} = 0$).

REFERENCES

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